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AUTOMOBILE ROADS AND ITS SIGNIFICANCE IN SOCIO-ECONOMIC LIFE

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Abstract. *The role of highways in the economic development of the republic, the modern state of the highway network of the Republic of Uzbekistan, modern highways, construction of Uzbek national highways, road policy in the Republic.*

Key words: *car, road, road network, highway, road condition, road network development.*

**АВТОМОБИЛЬНЫЕ ДОРОГИ И ИХ ЗНАЧЕНИЕ В СОЦИАЛЬНО-
ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЙ ЖИЗНИ**

Аннотация. *Роль автомобильных дорог в экономическом развитии республики, современное состояние сети автомобильных дорог Республики Узбекистан, современные автомобильные дороги, строительство узбекских национальных автомагистралей, дорожная политика в республике.*

Ключевые слова: *автомобиль, дорога, дорожная сеть, автомагистраль, состояние дорог, развитие дорожной сети.*

The role of highways in the economic development of the republic. According to the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan PF-535 of December 20, 2006, "The program for the development of public highways of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2007-2010 and in the long-term future", the construction of international transport corridors that provide the conditions for the economic development of the republic, transit and issues such as ensuring reliable transport connections between regions, forming a unified transport environment of the republic, restoring the Great Silk Road and entering the world market are defined as the priority tasks of the state road policy. The practical solution to these tasks is to improve the quality of transport and use of the existing road network, to harmonize the technical and operational conditions of the roads with the requirements of road users, to ensure the comfort and safety of the driving conditions of cars, and to effectively organize road maintenance works. requires. The economic development and progress of our republic depends, first of all, on the state of transport communications. As stated by the first President I. Karimov, "Now that we are an independent country, first of all we need to put communications in place."

If communication networks do not develop, Uzbekistan will not have a future.

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Development of transport communications and improvement of their use is one of the most urgent tasks in strengthening the independence of our Republic and developing its economy.

The fact that 83 percent of national economy goods transported by transport across the republic is accounted for by highways shows that highways are one of the main factors in the development of the republic's economy.

The geographical location of the republic requires that the main transport corridors for entering the world market and developing foreign economic relations are roads and railways.

Establishing international transport corridors that provide the conditions for the economic development of the republic, ensuring transit and reliable transport connections between regions, forming a single transport environment of the republic that is externally integrated and internally integrated, in addition, the restoration of the Great Silk Road and the world issues such as entering the market are among the priority tasks of the state road policy. 2. Modern state of the highway network of the Republic of Uzbekistan. At the beginning of the century, there were 27,000 kilometers of horse and cart roads in Uzbekistan, and by 1927, the total length of state roads in Central Asia was 5,313 km, including 923 km in Uzbekistan. reached

In 1931, a new method of gravel coating was tested at the road test site in Samarkand. In some places, the bitumen dilution method fully justified itself. In 1932, roads were built in this way in Bukhara as well. In 1932, with the opening of an oil field rich in heavy tar in the south of Uzbekistan (Jharkurghan), it began to be used instead of liquid bitumen. In 1928-1932, the first Bukhara-Gizhduvan-Kyziltepa black-surfaced road with a length of 62 km was built in Uzbekistan, in the same years Samarkand-Panjakent, Piskent-Almaliq, Tashkent-Piskent-Murotali, with a length of 48 km, KokanShorsuv-Andijan-Kuyganyar and other roads were built.

In 1937, there were 22,000 road junctions in the Republic, including 2,200 km of paved roads. In 1933-37, the length of paved roads accounted for 8% of the total road network.

In 1939, the construction of large structures using the Xalq Hashar road became popular in Uzbekistan, and this method was also widely used in road construction. In 1940, a special decision was made to build the Great Uzbek Tract with a length of 708 km. 326 km of this road were built by Tashkent, 222 km by Samarkand, and 162 km by Bukhara regions, and the construction was completed in April 1941. By the end of 1940, the road network with a hard surface was 4700 km.

Years, the total length of roads, roads of international importance, roads of state importance, roads of regional importance, roads of local importance, roads with cement concrete pavement, roads with asphalt concrete pavement, roads with black pavement, construction and use of roads in 1970-75 The production base of the organizations has been greatly improved, their

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palaces have been filled with new machines and mechanisms. Facilities of the road construction industry producing asphalt concrete, prefabricated reinforced concrete structures for building bridges, processing inert materials and improving their quality were put into operation, and as a result, some conditions were created to follow the technological discipline in construction. The length of public highways was 1976 In 2016, the total number of roads was 19,643 km, including 1,656 km of national roads, 7,203 km of national roads, and 10,975 km of local roads. 1975-80 were the years of the fastest growth in the road industry. The length of public highways reached 31,208 km, or 1,656 km of international highways, 12,164 km of national highways, and 17,388 km of local highways. In 1976 - 1981, a total of 4,400 km of new roads were built and reconstructed.

In these years, a lot of attention was paid to the construction of ring roads bypassing cities.

Today's state of use of the public highway network does not satisfy the demand of cars and road users. The reason for this is that the issue of repairing and maintaining roads in the republic in a short period of time remains unresolved. The lack of funds allocated for the current repair and maintenance of highways leads to the incomplete completion of works, moreover, to the decrease in the quality of completed works. As a result, there is a need for premature repairs on the roads.

This requires large-scale road repair works. Modern highways. Motor highways are roads designed for rapid transportation of passengers and cargo by cars at high speeds without being disturbed by oncoming vehicles and local traffic. These are highly improved, but expensive roads, which form the main skeleton of road networks of various countries and make up at most 1.5-2% of the length of road networks. The main requirement for the highways is to divide the traffic flow into an independent section for the opposite flows of cars, the absence of intersections at the same level, and to minimize the impact of individual cars entering or turning aside from it on the main flow traffic mode. It is forbidden to drive slow-moving vehicles, tractors, motorcycles, bicycles and horse-drawn carriages on highways. According to the classification of roads, highways include Ia category roads.

Motorways are usually built in two carriageways separated by a dividing strip. Each carriageway is designed for movement in one direction and includes the possibility of overtaking, so it is considered for the movement of at least two rows of cars. There are no traffic lights, traffic lights, and speed limit signs on highways. Motor highways can be entered from other roads only through a special connecting road equipped with additional lanes for acceleration or deceleration, which allow incoming vehicles to move at speeds corresponding to the speed of traffic on the highway and only then merge into the flow of vehicles without hindrance. gives

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"Bedabarsimon" level crossing on the modern freeway. In order to avoid the destruction of local traffic and pedestrians, the highways are bypassed by populated areas, and access roads to them are made only by roads with a high traffic speed. It is done only at intersections. Local roads cross the highways at different levels, while no downhill roads are made. Since highways are designed for long-distance transportation, gas stations, technical and medical service points, hotels, and kitchens are located along the road. Parking areas will be equipped for short-term rest of the drivers next to the road.

Construction of Uzbek national highways. Due to the need to build highways in Uzbekistan, comprehensive works and projects are being implemented in this matter in recent years. In particular, the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 22, 2009 No. PQ-1103 "On measures for the development and reconstruction of Uzbek national highways in 2009-2014" initiated the construction of highways in Uzbekistan. A number of decisions and orders of the following years are the basis for the development and acceleration of these works, in particular: Despite the fact that modern passenger cars increase their speed greatly in favorable road conditions, the design speed of highways is assumed to be between 120 and 150 km/h. - Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 22.10.2009 No. 277 "On measures - activities for the development of road infrastructure and service along Uzbek national highways;

- Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 03.05.2010 No. PQ-1331 "Development of regional highways. Decision on measures to implement multi-tranche financing program of the Phase 2 project with the participation of the Asian Development Bank;

- Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 21.12.2010 No. PQ-1446 "On accelerating the development of infrastructures, transport and communication construction in 2011-2015"; - Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 6, 2015 No. PQ-2313 "On the program for development and modernization of engineering communication and road transport infrastructure in 2015-2019". 5. Road policy carried out in the republic. In 1992, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Motorways" was adopted for the first time in our republic.

This law established the legal basis for the regulation of social relations in the field of development and use of the highway network in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

On January 26, 1993, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the establishment of the state joint-stock concern for the construction and use of highways of Uzbekistan (Ozavtoyol)" initiated reforms in the road sector. "Ozavtoyol" was transformed into a concern company by the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan issued

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on August 23, 2003, in order to ensure the implementation of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-3292 dated 19.08.2003 "On improving the management system for the construction and use of public highways". President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev decided to create an effective system of road management based on a comprehensive approach to the design, construction and use of roads and artificial structures, to improve their financing system, to create a competent customer service that allows to improve the quality of design and road construction works. Many resolutions were signed. For example, on February 14, 2017, the decree No. PF-4954 "On measures to further improve the traffic management system", in order to ensure the implementation of this decree, "Roads of the Republic of Uzbekistan" Resolution No. PQ-2776, May 2, 2017, "On the organization of the activities of the Republican Road Fund under the State Committee and the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan" Decision No. PQ-2946 can be cited.

Today, the main task facing the road workers of Uzbekistan is to build and develop transport communications that expand the opportunities to enter the world market.

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